

Deliverable 4.4

CAPACITY BUILDING AND HELPDESK

Design, implementation, and outcomes of the CHORIZO project's capacity building programme on using social norms to reduce food waste

Capacity Building and Helpdesk

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Glossary of terms and acronyms

Acronym/Term	Description
OFLW	Zero Food Loss & Waste
CB	Capacity Building
CS	Case Study
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
FLW	Food Loss & Waste
FW	Food Waste
GA	Grant Agreement
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MOA	Motivation, Opportunity, Ability
OTH	Other
PU	Public
R	Report
SN	Social Norm(s)
WP	Work Package

Executive summary

This deliverable describes the design, implementation, and outcomes of the CHORIZO project's capacity building programme and helpdesk service, developed to support actors across the food system in applying social norm-informed approaches to reduce food loss and waste (FLW). CHORIZO — Changing practices and Habits through Open, Responsible, and social Innovation towards ZerO food waste — is a project which recognizes that social norms play a pivotal role in shaping everyday behaviours, and that changing these norms can be a powerful lever for sustainable food practices. To operationalize this insight, the project developed a practical 8-step approach to guide the planning and execution of social norm informed behaviour change interventions and of a respective capacity building programme.

The capacity building programme was designed as key mechanism for CHORIZO to translate its research and tools into actionable knowledge for food system actors. Designed to bridge the gap between academic insight and real-world application, the programme targeted a broad range of stakeholders, including policymakers, civil society organisations, local authorities, school and food service actors, food banks and researchers. Its primary aim was to build and improve the capacity of these actors to understand, design, and implement food waste interventions that are rooted in behavioural science, and more specifically, in the dynamics of social norms.

The 8-step approach—central to all training activities—provided a clear, structured framework that participants could follow to create their own social norm-informed interventions. To support this, the programme offered a combination of online and face-to-face formats, including two in-person workshops and five online sessions. These were tailored to the needs of specific sectors and enriched with relevant project outputs such as the CHORIZO DataHub, Visualizer, educational materials, and actor-specific guidance documents.

The last part of the programme was the DeepAction session, a hands-on workshop in which participants applied the 8-step approach to real-world scenarios focused on reducing food waste. This practical exercise helped to solidify theoretical learning, deepen participants' understanding of how to identify and shift social norms, and encourage collaborative intervention design.

Throughout the programme, CHORIZO emphasized participatory and inclusive learning, informed by a comprehensive needs assessment and guided by the Motivation-Opportunity-Ability (MOA) framework to understand the target groups and participants' behaviours. A total of 217 stakeholders registered for the sessions, with 129 actively participating. Feedback from these sessions was consistently positive, with all respondents rating the experience as high quality and expressing appreciation for the clarity, relevance, and applicability of the content. The tools introduced were also well received, although some participants indicated a need for more time and support to integrate them fully into their work.

While the helpdesk function received less engagement than anticipated—likely due to its more individualized and on-demand format—the project nonetheless fulfilled its commitment to providing follow-up support and fostering continued dialogue through resources such as a LinkedIn community and online resource library.

In sum, the CHORIZO capacity building programme successfully achieved its objective of making complex behavioural science concepts accessible and actionable for practitioners seeking to engage more and more effectively in FLW prevention and reduction. By focusing on the role of social norms and equipping actors with a structured method to design and evaluate interventions, the programme laid a strong foundation for considering behaviour change techniques in their FLW interventions and applying the CHORIZO results.

1 Introduction

The EU-funded CHORIZO project (Changing practices and Habits through Open, Responsible, and social Innovation towards ZerO food waste) seeks to reduce food loss and waste (FLW) by leveraging social norm informed behavioural insights and data-driven approaches to improve decision-making across the food system. This deliverable (D4.4) presents the design, implementation, and outcomes of the project’s capacity building programme and helpdesk service.

1.1 What is in for you?

This document provides detailed information about the design, implementation, and outcomes of the CHORIZO project’s capacity building programme on using social norms to reduce food waste. It can also serve as instructions on how to set up and run a capacity building programme and helpdesk service on social norm informed behaviour change.

- If you are planning to **run your own** social-norm informed capacity building programme, and are seeking guidance and advice, you can find the slide deck and 8-step approach in the annex (Chapter 7). Building upon the feedback section (Chapter 3.5) and the lessons learned and recommendations (Chapter 5) you can learn from our mistakes and make it even better.
- If you are interested in assessing the **outcomes** of the capacity building and help desk function, chapter 2.3 holds an overview on the task objectives and aims and chapter 3.1 to 3.4 explains how they were achieved.
- Do you want to **improve the framework conditions** for social norm research and practice for FLW reduction? Then please especially read chapter 5 Lessons learned and recommendations, and chapter 6 conclusions.

1.2 Background and context

While technical tools and data frameworks are essential outputs of the CHORIZO project, their impact is contingent on the ability of end-users—ranging from policymakers and industry actors to civil society organisations—to understand, adopt, and apply them in real-world contexts. Therefore, the project designed a comprehensive capacity building programme and a complementary helpdesk. These mechanisms were intended to support the uptake of CHORIZO results, foster dialogue and knowledge transfer among stakeholders, increase their engagement and ensure lasting impact beyond the project’s lifespan. CHORIZO results and tools, which were introduced in the capacity building programme to the participants, were the CHORIZO DataHub, the FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool/ Visualiser, the project’s communication projects, the work package (WP) 4 educational products, and previous deliverables, mainly the Deliverable 4.1 Actor Specific Guidance.

1.3 Objectives of the Capacity Building and Helpdesk

Two main objectives of work package (WP) 4 “Actor-, context- & gender-specific change fostering” relate to the capacity building programme and helpdesk service and were mentioned in the grant agreement. The following table (1) puts together these two objectives, the aims and expected outcomes, including results and impact pathways that were connected to this task and deliverable in the grant agreement.

WP4 “Actor-, context- & gender-specific change fostering” **objectives:**

(1) Apply behaviour change theory and the mechanisms linking social norms to FLW behaviour revealed in WP3 “Predictive analytics & modelling backbone for changing social norms towards

0FLW”] into concrete change fostering actions, by taking into consideration the motivations, opportunities, and abilities of sectoral food system actors.

[...]

(4) Support the uptake of sector-specific guidance of CHORIZO by building the capacity of the target actors.

Aims & Outcomes: To fulfil these objectives, the CHORIZO **capacity building programme** aimed to:

1. Support the uptake of actor-specific guidance (D4.1),
2. Identify specific capacity gaps of food chain actors and inform the content of corresponding capacity building activities (T4.4)
3. Design a capacity building programme (incl. 2 face-to-face workshops and 3 webinars) and offer it to more than 200 food chain actors in order to build their capacities,
 - 3.1. generally for considering behaviour change techniques in their FLW interventions
 - 3.2. and specifically, to apply the CHORIZO results
4. Provide stakeholders with the skills and knowledge to interpret and use the data, tools, and recommendations developed by the project;

The **helpdesk service** aimed to:

5. Enable a two-way communication stream with the actors via a ‘help-desk’ function for externals (including, though not only, similar EU projects and initiatives),
6. Offer digital and personalized coaching as well as networking opportunities on demand

Table 1 Objectives, aims and expected outcomes of capacity building programme and helpdesk. Collection of respective references from the CHORIZO Grant Agreement (GA).

Project partner ICLEI was foreseen to act as multiplier particularly to local authorities in integrating behaviour change knowledge into their FLW prevention/reduction strategies and outreach, to foster according social norms.

Together, these efforts were meant to ensure that CHORIZO’s innovations are not only theoretically robust but also practically accessible and actionable. The following sections report on how the original objectives and aims foreseen in the CHORIZO GA (see Table 1) have been achieved and describe the content, delivery formats, and feedback underpinning both the capacity building and helpdesk components.

2 Capacity Building Programme

This chapter guides through how and why the capacity building programme was designed (Chapter 3.1 Concept), what content was developed to fit the concept (Chapter 3.2 Content) and how the programme was implemented (Chapter 3.3 Implementation and Outreach). Chapter 3.4 gives a practical example of one of the sessions and Chapter 3.5 is all about the participants' feedback.

2.1 Concept

“Apply behaviour change theory and linking social norms to FLW behaviour into concrete change fostering actions.” (Objective 1 - see Table 1)

To meet this objective, the CHORIZO Capacity Building Programme was designed to equip key stakeholders with the knowledge, skills, and tools needed to understand, apply, and amplify the project's outputs in efforts to reduce FLW. The idea was to serve as a bridge between the research and innovation outputs of the project (e.g. data tools, behavioural insights, policy recommendations) and the real-world contexts in which they are to be implemented.

“Design a capacity building programme generally for considering behaviour change techniques in FLW interventions.” (Aim 3.1 - see Table 1)

The capacity building programme concept brought together the CHORIZO project results, insights and tools with the conceptual framework of the proven “Academy of Change”¹ concept, a prior work by the CSCP team. The “Academy of Change” and also its German follow up “weiter_wirken” were conducted between 2018 and 2023 with more than 60 international civil society organisations involved. The CSCP team used the programme outline and checklists from these projects and transferred it into 6 steps of the CHORIZO Plan to run food waste interventions and added 2 steps specifically focussing on how to include social norms into behaviour change interventions.

“Taking into consideration the motivations, opportunities, and abilities of sectoral food system actors.” (Objective 1.1 - see Table 1)

The CHORIZO project used the MOA framework² throughout its activities. In the MOA framework, aspects of motivation, opportunity and ability are combined to determine if and how a person behaves in any given situation. In line with behavioural change scientists, CHORIZO believes that behavioural change is based on an interplay of these three factors. While it can be used to understand why a person wastes food, it can also serve to understand why, or why not a person joins a capacity building programme or what skills, inspiration or guidance a person could require to engage in actions to reduce food waste.

In preparation of the capacity building programme a stakeholder mapping was conducted via desk research to list potential participant groups, define their needs and to tailor the programme to these needs. As part of this stakeholder mapping, their potential motivations, opportunities and abilities were also added into the excel file and verified with a needs assessment survey and interviews (see below). The MOA stayed a backbone of the conceptual approach to constantly verify if the programme will be accessible and fitting to the target groups interest.

¹ The Academy of Change is a capacity building programme on sustainable behaviours designed for future leaders working on climate change and sustainability within the NGO sector (<https://aochange.org/>).

² Ölander, F., & Thøgersen, J. (1995). Understanding of consumer behaviour as a prerequisite for environmental protection. Journal of consumer policy, 18(4), 345-385.

“Identify specific capacity gaps of food chain actors and inform the content of corresponding capacity building activities.” (Aim 2 - see Table 1)

A literature review of communication, education and other capacity building programmes on FLW and Social Norms was conducted and a needs assessment survey and interviews identified gaps of food chain actors, to inform the programme content and to meet the actors’ needs (see Figure 1 for the advertisement of the needs assessment survey). There were many training opportunities on FLW and Behaviour Change interventions, but none in this unique combination with social norms. The needs assessment survey supported these findings, although participants showed some experience in working with social norms: 33% of respondents have worked with social norms as part of their FLW initiatives and 7% worked with social norms in other fields. They wished for hands-on tools and information (like a workbook) for understanding social norms and how to use them, collaborations with other actors, training for food service, retail, schools and generally a how-to use language in interventions. The interviews highlighted a need for training material and opportunities in local language to foster institutional change. Translation in different local languages of the materials and programme sessions was not foreseen in the project, but added as a recommendation for future projects into the recommendations section.

Figure 1 LinkedIn post to advertise the needs assessment survey

2.2 Content

“Support the uptake of sector-specific guidance” (Objective 2 - see Table 1)

“Support the uptake of actor-specific guidance (D4.1)” (Aim 1 - see Table 1)

Theoretical and informative backbone of the Capacity Building Programme was the actor specific guidance (CHORIZO Deliverable 4.1). This guidance brought together all the social norm knowledge and insights from the CHORIZO project in a series of guidance documents, targeted to specific actors. It already introduced the 8-step approach of running social norm informed behaviour change interventions. As shown in Figure 2, the 8 steps include: (1) define your objective, (2) understand your target group, (3) determine relevant social norms—are they descriptive (what people do) or injunctive (what people feel they should do)?, (4) choose the right approach —do you want to strengthen,

change, or create a norm?, (5) plan the intervention, (6) do a reality check, (7) implement, and (8) evaluate the impact. The programme was also inspired by methodological frameworks like the MOA.

Figure 2 8-step approach for designing social norm informed interventions (developed by CSCP)

“Design a Capacity Building Programme specifically to apply the CHORIZO results” (Aim 3.2. - see Table 1)

In addition to D4.1, further content for the capacity building programme was drawn from D1.4 Sector-specific Guidance, D2.3 Empirical evidence sense-making (compiling the Case Study results), project newsletters and fact sheets. Within the different capacity building sessions, CHORIZO tools were presented within the thematically fitting sessions. The FW educational boardgame and the teaching and education material for school teachers (“Hack your school lunch”) was presented in the school food session by UCPH. Insights from the CHORIZO Food Bank Case Study were presented in the food bank session by HFBA. The designed version of the Cities Guidance was presented in the city’s session by ICLEI. The Datahub and the Visualizer was presented to all actors, and the participants of the DeepAction Session got an even deeper look into the Visualizer. Wherever possible, we also included information and insights about gendered aspects of FLW derived from the project.

“Provide stakeholders with the skills and knowledge to interpret and use the data, tools, and recommendations developed by the project” (Aim 4 - see Table 1)

In order to equip the stakeholders in an efficient manner, the programme was split into two building blocks:

1. The **compact capacity building session** provided the theory and insights on social norms and social norm informed intervention design. It represented a compact bundle of knowledge, each targeted to specific actor groups and with interaction and group work formats to apply the learnings.
2. An **optional DeepAction session** was a much more practical, hands-on session to support the participants in designing and planning their own social norm informed intervention.

Both sessions were designed to be participatory, inclusive, and adaptable to the needs of different target groups, including policy-makers, school food actors, food chain actors, researchers, NGOs, and local authorities. The different tools were presented to the participants and shared with them in a resource library on Miro throughout the project (Figure 3).

Figure 3 CHORIZO resource library on Miro, shared with the participants

2.3 Implementation and outreach

“Design a capacity building programme (incl. 2 face-to-face workshops and 3 webinars) and offer it to more than 200 food chain actors in order to build their capacities” (Aim 3 - see Table 1)

As mentioned in chapter 3.1, a needs assessment survey was conducted to tailor the programme to the participants needs and wishes. Within this, participants were also asked about the delivery format, interaction and dissemination preferences. This is how they ranked the “following formats in terms of how likely [they] would be to use them (top = most likely)”:

1. **Online workshop/training session with actors from my sector** (47% put as top preference)
2. **Online workshop/training session with actors from different sectors**
3. **In-person workshop/training session with actors from my sector**
4. **In-person workshop/training session with actors from different sectors** (but 32% put in place 9)

5. **Online workspace** (e.g. online whiteboard, including exercises to become familiar with the content and methods) to work through independently or in a peer group (32% put in place 5)
6. **Printable workbook** (including exercises to become familiar with the content and methods) to work through independently
7. **Online forum** to discuss with peers
8. **Webinars** to share **best-practices** with peers
9. **Q&A webinars** with the CHORIZO team (32% put in place 9)
10. **'Help-desk'** contact to ask questions and get support from the CHORIZO team (58% put in last place)

To make sure to integrate this feedback, and also to deliver what was promised in the GA, most of the sessions were offered sector-specific (Food Service, Schools, Food Banks, Cities) and one also targeted for all actors together. These considerations were supplemented by interviews with some of the survey participants who allowed the CHORIZO team to contact them. The interviewees highlighted that if the aim is to reach ministries and local actors, the programme language should be adapted to the local language. This was mostly out of scope for the programme, but one of the sessions – the in-person session for food service actors – was still offered in the local language German.

As shown in Table 2, two in-person and five online sessions were organised and the team reached out to more than 200 actors and enabled TRL5 “Training validated in relevant environment” with the capacity building programme, as promised.

Session	Date	Delivery	Registrations	No of participants
<i>Food service</i>	17.3.25	In person	Not applicable	7
<i>School food actors</i>	7.5.25	online	43	38
<i>All actors 1</i>	21.5.25	online	48	17
<i>All actors 2</i>	21.5.25	In person	13	7
<i>City actors</i>	11.6.25	online	59	37
<i>Food bank actors</i>	27.6.25	online	43	20
<i>DeepAction Session</i>	2.7.25	online	11	3
TOTAL			217	129

Table 2 Overview on capacity building sessions delivered, incl. number of registrations and participation.

Over 20 posts on LinkedIn (see Figure 4) and 3 newsletter items were created by the CSCP team to promote the programme and were also widely shared by the consortium partners. All reached out to contacts to invite them to join the programme.

Figure 4 LinkedIn post to advertise the programme

On the CHORIZO website, the Helpdesk was set up as a one-stop-shop where visitors can find all relevant information and links for the capacity building and Helpdesk functions, like the email address where they can reach the team with their questions and ask for feedback on their intervention design (Figure 5). The project team also created a LinkedIn group for the participants of the capacity building sessions, CHORIZO project partners and other interested FLW actors to exchange and engage more in OFLW and social norm informed actions.

Figure 5 Helpdesk page on the CHORIZO website (<https://chorizoproject.eu/helpdesk/>)

Participants received a certificate of attendance after each of the sessions they joined. This was meant to nudge them to fill the feedback survey, but since the survey needed to stay anonymous, the certificates were sent to every participant of the capacity building session. It is unclear if the announcement of the certificates increased participation in the feedback survey.

2.4 Insights into the CHORIZO DeepAction Session

“Apply behaviour change theory into concrete change fostering actions.” (Objective 1 - see Table 1)

The CHORIZO DeepAction session offered a valuable opportunity to translate social norm informed behavioural theory into practice. As part of the Chorizo Capacity Building Programme, participants were guided through the 8 steps approach for social norms informed intervention theory and piloted their ideas of intervention into reducing food waste real case examples into practice.

The session aimed to foster applied learning, strengthen participants’ understanding of how social norms can change behaviours, and support the co-creation of actionable interventions in the food context relevant to real-life settings. Participants were asked to bring their own intervention idea and work collaboratively with other participants during the session.

The group focused on one intervention about reducing food waste in a primary school context and that aimed to encourage students to finish up their plates. To provide a clear practical approach the group went through the 8 steps intervention plan in order to apply the actions in real life settings. Here are the main key learnings from the Chorizo DeepAction Session hosted on July 2nd 2025:

- **Applied Learning:** Participants deepened their understanding of how social norms influence behaviour and co-created actionable interventions.
- **Case Focus:** The primary intervention targeted elementary school students, aiming to encourage them to finish their meals in the school canteen.
- **Behavioural Challenge:** Identifying the motivations behind plate-finishing behaviours was crucial. Key considerations included the potential impact of rewards, peer competition, and connections with food producers.
- **Social Norms Analysis:** Participants identified the unhelpful norm: “It’s okay to throw away food because it’s free.”
- **Intervention Strategies Explored:**
 1. Changing and reframing unhelpful norms with positive messaging (“Every meal matters...”).
 2. Promoting alternative helpful norms by highlighting peer role models.
 3. Introduce new norms by creating emotional connections through storytelling and motivational campaigns.
- **Implementation Planning:** The intervention is planned to be scheduled during lunch, in the school canteen, with messages delivered via stickers on lunch boxes.
- **Reality Check:** Before implementing, there is need for critical review and communication clarity, cultural appropriateness, inclusivity, and resource feasibility.
- **Next Steps:** The intervention is set for rollout, with subsequent evaluation planned to inform iterative improvements and potential scaling across other food settings.

This session highlighted the importance of combining theory with practical steps, especially understanding motivations and norms, to design effective behavioural interventions in food waste reduction. Some of the feedback received was that one of the favourites intervention strategies explored during the session is the reframing (1): “when well done, it can be really effective.”

2.5 Feedback of participants

After each capacity building session, participants were invited to share feedback via a survey form. This sub-chapter presents the feedback, highlighting how further capacity building programmes on FLW can be adapted to build on the experiences of the CHORIZO project. First, the survey results are reported on the capacity building session and the CHORIZO tools, before some general recommendations are made.

In total, 27 respondents provided feedback to the capacity building sessions. Of the 27 feedback survey responses, 25 were based on a standard questionnaire, handed out at most of the sessions. Only the session for food banks and the DeepAction session had a slightly different and shorter surveys due to their different nature. One additional response came in for the food-banks specific session and one additional response was handed in via the survey specifically designed for the DeepAction Session.

All feedback surveys followed a similar logic. In a first step, participants were asked to indicate in how many sessions they had participated so far. Afterwards, participants were asked to indicate how they would rate the capacity building experience on a 7-point Likert scale (see Annex for survey questions). In the short form survey for food banks, questions followed on the increased knowledge on social norms and the relationship with donors. In case of the standard survey, question followed regarding the selection of CHORIZO tools, and the added value of these tools. In case of the DeepAction feedback

survey, the survey was simplified to not include all CHORIZO tools, and focused on the Visualizer, which was integrated more directly in the session.

The 26 respondents to the standard and short feedback survey to the first segment of the capacity building were part of the following food-related actor groups.

Multiple respondents belonged to more than one food-related actor group. A notable group in the “Other” category included research actors.

Figure 6 Count of respondents by food-related actor groups (multiple answers possible, n = 26)

The respondents were asked to rank the overall quality of the capacity building session on a 7-point Likert scale, where 1 was understood as “very low quality”, 4 was defined as “average” and 7 was defined as “very high quality”. The aim was to at least receive a score of 5 or above on average.

Figure 7 shows the 26 results of the overall quality rating for the Capacity Building sessions. All respondents gave a rating of 5 or higher, with a median response of 6, which **infers a high quality perception of the Capacity Building sessions** of the first segment. In detail, 11 respondents rated the quality with 6, whereas 9 respondents gave a quality score of 5, and 6 respondents gave a quality score of 7.

Figure 7 Overall quality of the Capacity Building workshop (median of 6 on a 7-point Likert scale, n = 26)

Figure 8 shows the count of respondents who indicated usage or interest into the selected CHORIZO tools. This question was asked in the general survey only.

Figure 8 Count of respondents who used or are interested in using selected CHORIZO tools

On each of these tools, respondents were asked to provide feedback, again using 7-point Likert scales, with 7 indicating high usefulness and 1 indicating the opposite.

Of the 13 respondents, who reviewed the Miro Learning Environment, which was used during the Capacity Building sessions, but remained accessible to users afterwards, an average quality score of 5.9 was achieved, with the median response being 6. In two cases, a score of 4 was attributed, which likely resulted from the potential entry barrier presented by online whiteboard tools, since some

participants have less experience in using these tools. In these cases, a short introduction of the tool, or a dedicated board operator might be possible solutions.

For the DataHub, respondents gave an average score of 6 and a median of 6 when asked whether it provides a helpful reservoir of knowledge. All individual scores were 5 or higher, indicating broad recognition of its usefulness. When asked whether the DataHub will provide solutions to reduce food loss and waste (FLW) within their organisation, the average score was 5.8, with a median of 6. Slightly lower scores were observed for the question regarding the DataHub's relevance for organisational decision making, with an average of 5.4 and a median of 5.5. These slightly more cautious evaluations were attributed by respondents to a current lack of familiarity with the full range of available content or a need for more practical exposure before assessing the tool's impact on decision making.

Of the 9 respondents, who indicated usage or interest in the LinkedIn Group, the average score was 5.6 on the question whether respondents see it as a helpful tool to expand their network and exchange about experiences, problems, solutions to reduce food waste using social norms. The median was 5.5. Since most respondents took the feedback survey directly after the capacity building session, the practical exposure before assessing the tool's effectiveness was limited.

Of the 8 respondents who evaluated the Visualizer, the tool received an average score of 6, with a median of 6.5, in response to the question of whether it would be helpful for food waste-related decision making. This reflects a strong perceived potential for the tool to support informed choices in this area. When asked whether they would consider using the Visualizer to reduce food loss and waste within their organisation, the responses were slightly more reserved, with both the average and median scores at 5.5. This suggests that while the tool's usefulness is broadly acknowledged, its actual integration into organisational processes may depend on further familiarisation or context-specific needs.

Of the 5 respondents, who indicated interest in the CHORIZO Helpdesk, the average score was 5.6 and the median was 6 in response to the question whether they consider making use of the Helpdesk function to reduce food waste in their organisation. This indicates that the on-demand, bilateral exchange, offered by the Helpdesk might only be suitable for a limited audience. A potential entry barrier might be that the Helpdesk is designed to support intervention design. As a result, actors in an early stage of designing an intervention might not yet feel sufficiently prepared to engage with the Helpdesk.

Looking into open comments that were provided towards the end of the survey, the following findings were made. Firstly, several respondents noted that they had limited experience with the tools at the time of the survey, which made it difficult to provide conclusive feedback. Some participants expressed optimism about the usefulness of the tools once they had more time to engage with them. Feedback highlighted that while the Capacity Building was seen as interesting and valuable, a more focused agenda, more time for practical examples, and additional support during exercises — particularly in breakout sessions and when using Miro — would have enhanced the learning experience.

Since only one participant of the DeepAction planning responded to the feedback survey, the responses will not be analysed quantitatively. However, the respondent commented on the usefulness of the 8-step approach to the design of interventions, and overall had a good impression of CHORIZO and its products.

Based on the survey responses, the following recommendations can be made in order to continue supporting food supply chain actors on their journey to reduce food loss and waste:

- Integrating more time for interactive application of learned contents and the application of CHORIZO tools during the capacity building sessions can lead to higher levels of understanding and usage. The DeepAction session was specifically designed to provide a more hands-on experience.
- Breaking down complex processes, like designing and implementing behaviour-change interventions into step-by-step processes, such as the 8-steps to create social-norms based behaviour change interventions, were useful ways to provide actors with guidance for their own actions.
- The entry barrier to the Helpdesk might have been perceived as too high. Using more group-based formats, such as the LinkedIn group may lower the barrier of entry and encourage long-term engagement.

Overall, the CHORIZO tools were well appreciated by those who expressed their interest or stated that they had used the tool. Integrating the tools more prominently into the capacity building sessions could have increased the usage. However, it would have required reducing the time for behavioural insights and learning about food-waste related social norms. This illustrates conflicting goals. In the case of the CHORIZO Capacity Building sessions, this conflict was deliberately resolved to focus more on sharing knowledge about food-waste related social norms and how to design interventions to address them.

3 Helpdesk

The CHORIZO Helpdesk aimed to provide a two-way communication stream, to support actors in a tailored way to design and implement their own social-norms based interventions to reduce food waste. The Helpdesk was communicated to all participants of the Capacity Building sessions and further advertised in the LinkedIn Group.

The technical setup of the Helpdesk was designed to reduce entry barriers. To provide a low entry barrier, the Helpdesk was based on a central e-mail address (helpdesk.chorizo@cscp.org), which was publicly displayed on the CHORIZO website and advertised in the Capacity Building sessions. When entering the CHORIZO website, the Helpdesk function was directly visible in the menu bar. Upon clicking on the Helpdesk page, visitors were provided with information on how to use the Helpdesk. Further, when scrolling down, the website provides links to the LinkedIn Group, the other CHORIZO Capacity Building sessions, the DataHub and the CHORIZO publications.

Figure 9 CHORIZO Helpdesk as imbedded on the project's website.

Despite repeated advertisement in Capacity Building sessions and the LinkedIn Group, as well as the initial interest by 5 respondents to the feedback survey, we did not receive requests for support via the Helpdesk. One potential reason for this might be a perceived high barrier of entry. While the technological barrier of entry was kept at a minimum, the phrasing “help you to plan and implement” a social-norm based intervention on food waste may have been associated with a necessary high level of commitment.

Another reason for the low usage might be that potential target groups did not have demand for a Helpdesk. After performing a needs assessment survey, the Helpdesk was ranked as the least requested tool by 58% of respondents. Consequently, the Capacity Building was designed to equip the participants with all necessary steps to plan and implement social-norms based interventions.

4 Lessons learned and recommendations

Setting up and running a capacity building programme is an inspiring and diverse work, and in the meantime very time-consuming. Especially when the programme has the aim of including many project results into its training materials it needs to happen at the very end of the project and preparations depend on tasks and results of other work packages. Starting this task earlier than the foreseen M26 would have eased the process.

- **Advertisement** is key and should be diversified in several channels, also as direct messages to potential participants. Especially if the aim is to reach a diverse target group and create an inclusive programme, it is useful to step out of the own bubble and try out new formats of outreach. To take care of this the CHORIZO team shared the upcoming programme at a festival for people working in food and farming within a format called “swarm intelligence room”, a really intense space to pitch ideas and get immediate feedback or contact details by participants.
- **Actor engagement:** The LinkedIn group, which was set up to engage peer-to-peer exchange between OFLW and social norm practitioners was only slowly kicking off and is still mainly dependent on the team’s involvement and engaging posts in the group. Since no resources are foreseen to follow up on this group after the project ends in September 2025, there are low expectations on much interaction there after the project. Also, the Help Desk function was barely used, and the feedback survey was filled by about 20% of participants. It remains unclear, if the nudge to receive a certificate of attendance after filling the survey led to a greater fill-in rate.
- **Balancing theoretical and practical content:** The team decided to limit the general capacity building session to 2,5 hours to facilitate participation and increase accessibility. The theoretical understanding was a relevant base for the more practical parts of the rest of the session. Participants wished for more practical sessions, but only 3 participants joined the very hands-on DeepAction session that was planned as a follow up. This could be still due to the extreme heat that day, but also raises the question of actor engagement, when it comes to them taking action.

Overall CHORIZO confirmed that social norms are valuable tools to scale behaviour change interventions towards OFLW. However, there is a lack of evidence on the effectiveness of the different social norm informed messages used in intervention design. This is due to the diversity of factors influencing people’s resonance to these messages. Further research and especially testing of the impact of different social norm informed messages is highly recommended. Additionally, the team did not find much evidence on gendered differences in the reception of social norm informed interventions. The project did not have the scope to also include other aspects of diversity and inclusion into its research, but this is seen to also improve the uptake of behaviour change interventions. The project did also not plan in for translating the materials and running the sessions in local languages. This could have also improved the outreach of and participation in the programme. Generally, social norms were found to be an interesting tool to understand and increase the uptake of behaviour change interventions and should be further researched.

5 Conclusions

The CHORIZO project has clearly demonstrated that social norms are a crucial but often overlooked dimension in addressing FLW. By designing and delivering a comprehensive capacity building programme rooted in behavioural science, CHORIZO successfully equipped food system actors with the tools and knowledge to design interventions that not only inform but also shift behaviour.

Central to the project's impact was the development and implementation of the 8-step approach, which uniquely integrates social norms into behavioural intervention planning. This framework allowed stakeholders to diagnose and target existing norms or establish new, constructive ones in order to foster more sustainable food practices. The participatory and context-specific format of the programme enabled effective learning and application, as reflected in the positive participant feedback.

Importantly, the project acknowledged that capacity building is not a one-size-fits-all process. Tailoring sessions to different actor groups, using accessible digital tools, and creating hands-on learning experiences (like the DeepAction session) were essential to the programme's success. While uptake of the Helpdesk function was limited, this underscored the importance of perceived readiness and timing in an actor's journey toward intervention design.

CHORIZO also highlighted critical areas for future work, including more evidence on the effectiveness of social norm-based messaging, the role of gender and inclusion, and strategies for reducing barriers to tool engagement. These insights suggest that social norm-informed interventions hold great potential—but must be accompanied by adequate training, contextual sensitivity, and iterative feedback mechanisms to achieve lasting change.

In conclusion, CHORIZO's capacity building efforts provide a replicable model for integrating behavioural science into FLW reduction. By empowering stakeholders to not only understand but also influence the social norms within their sectors, the project contributes meaningfully toward the EU's broader sustainability and zero food waste goals.

6 Annex

Feedback Survey Questions

Likert-scale values:

- 1, Strongly disagree
- 2, disagree
- 3, Somewhat disagree
- 4, Neither agree nor disagree
- 5, Somewhat agree
- 6, Agree
- 7, Strongly Agree
- + Opt. out option: I don't know OR this does not apply to me.

- (1) Please indicate in how many capacity training sessions you have participated:
 - a. 0
 - b. 1
 - c. 2
 - d. More than 2
- (2) How would you rate the overall quality of the CHORIZO capacity building?
- (3) Please select which food-related actor group(s) you are part of (you can select multiple)
 - a. Cities (incl. city administration, municipal companies)
 - b. Schools (incl. higher education)
 - c. Food Banks
 - d. Food Services (incl. Restaurants, Hotels, Catering)
 - e. Private households and consumers (incl. representative organisations)
 - f. Packaging and Processing
 - g. Retail and Wholesale
 - h. Other (semi-open)
- (4) Please select all CHORIZO tools that you have used, or are planning to use very soon (you can select multiple)
 - a. CHORIZO Visualiser (FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool)
 - b. CHORIZO Datahub
 - c. CHORIZO Peer Exchange LinkedIn Group
 - d. CHORIZO Digital Learning Environment on Miro

- e. CHORIZO Helpdesk (Bilateral support to implement a social-norm related food waste reduction action).

(5) Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements regarding the **Capacity Building Programme**: (Matrix / Grid, statements listed on the left with Likert scale to the right. With logic, based on the answers of the previous question.)

- a. The Capacity Building has increased my knowledge on social norms.
- b. The Capacity Building will contribute to decisions that I make within my organisation to reduce food waste.
- c. The Capacity Building will increase my engagement towards food waste reduction.
- d. I see the CHORIZO Peer Exchange LinkedIn Group as a helpful tool to exchange about experiences, problems, and solutions to reduce food waste using social norms.
- e. I will consult the digital learning environment on miro also after the capacity building programme finishes.
- f. I will consider contacting the Chorizo Helpdesk in order to find solutions to reduce food waste in my organisation.

(6) Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements regarding the **Chorizo Project**: (Matrix / Grid, statements listed on the left with Likert scale to the right. With logic, based on the answers of the previous question.)

- a. The FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool provides helpful information for food waste-related decision making.
- b. I will consider using the FLW Rapid Appraisal Tool in order to find solutions to reduce food waste in my organisation.
- c. The Chorizo Datahub provides me with a helpful reservoir of knowledge about food waste reducing actions I can implement in my organisation.
- d. I will consider using the Chorizo Datahub in order to find solutions to reduce food waste in my organisation.
- e. Using the Datahub of identified actions addressing food loss and waste (available on the CHORIZO project public website), has contributed to providing information relevant to decision-making in my work or research.
- f. The CHORIZO communication products and channels (Newsletter, Factsheets, LinkedIn etc) have increased my engagement in FLW initiatives.

8-Steps Handout

CHORIZO Capacity Building Outline of our 8 step approach for social norm informed interventions

Slides of the Capacity Building (all actors session)

Capacity Building

On using social norms to reduce food waste

House-Rules

To help create a welcoming and productive space for everyone, we kindly ask that you:

- Be kind to others and to yourself :)
- Keep your microphone muted when you're not speaking
- Use "raise hand" function or use the chat to contribute
- Keep your camera on if you feel comfortable, it helps us all connect better!
- Put your mobile phone aside, switch off all notifications and messaging apps on your computer

While waiting:

Please change your name to show your name, organisation and pronouns (if you like)

The good provider social norm
What if less is more?

Photo by Connor Danylenko on Pexels

**The good provider social norm
What if less is more?**

Photo by Connor Danylenko on Pexels

What you will learn today:

- **Explore** what Social Norms are and where we can identify them
- **Work** with Social Norms

Photo by jchizhe on Pexels

Our purpose for today's session:

- Raise **awareness** to recognise social norms in your working context and everyday life
- Deepen your **understanding** on social norms
- Learning from **examples** to plan your next interventions

CHORIZO project

Changing practices and Habits through Open, Responsible, and social Innovation towards ZerO food waste

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITA DI BOLOGNA

Let's check-in:

Which **sector** do you belong to? (multi answer is possible)

Who has already **implemented interventions to reduce food waste** in their own company or everyday life?

Who has already dealt with **social norms** in their own company or everyday life?

Agenda

- What are Social Norms?
- How to Use Social Norms in Behavioral Change Interventions?
- Plan an Intervention
- Chorizo Tools
- Next Steps and Check-out

WHAT are Social Norms?

Learning through examples

What are social norms?

“Social norms are unwritten rules which influence people’s everyday behaviour.”

Photo by [Priscilla Du Preez](#) on [Unsplash](#)

10

How do social norms work?

Conform with what you think is expected (injunctive)

Copy observed behaviours (descriptive)

Photo by [Priscilla Du Preez](#) on [Unsplash](#)

What can be effects of social norms?

Helpful

Photo by [Priscilla Du Preez](#) on [Unsplash](#)

Unhelpful

SOCIAL NORMS

“Social norms are unwritten rules which influence people’s everyday behaviour.”

Conform with what you think is expected (injunctive)

Copy observed behaviours (descriptive)

Helpful

Unhelpful

Photo by [Priscilla Du Preez](#) on [Unsplash](#)

What are the social norms at play in different settings?

Schools

Food Service

Cities

Food Banks

What are the social norms at play in SCHOOL settings?

„Good Provider“

„Adapt to peer behaviour“

„Good Child“

“Suboptimal food”

INJUNCTIVE: Conform with what you think is expected

DESCRIPTIVE: Copy observed behaviours

What are the social norms at play in FOOD SERVICE settings?

„Good Provider“

“Suboptimal food”

„Take leftovers home“

INJUNCTIVE: Conform with what you think is expected

DESCRIPTIVE: Copy observed behaviours

What are the social norms at play in CITY settings?

„Good Provider“

„Visually perfect is preferable“

„Create new norms through incentives or penalties“

„Adapting to neighbours behaviours“

INJUNCTIVE: Conform with what you think is expected

DESCRIPTIVE: Copy observed behaviours

What are the social norms at play in FOOD BANK settings?

INJUNCTIVE: Conform with what you think is expected

DESCRIPTIVE: Copy observed behaviours

Miro & Breakout Rooms

Over to you!

Time to apply what you just learned!

1 Identifying social norms in your contexts

Instructions:

In your group:

- think and discuss what norms you identify in your contexts
- add them as sticky notes
- Please self-organized in your groups

Miro & Breakout Rooms

How to get there:

1. click on the miro [link](#) in the chat
2. click "join break out room" in zoom
3. on miro: go to board 1 and click the arrow next to your group number

Setting:

- the pictures serve as inspiration
- It's a self-organized group work

Miro & Breakout Rooms

What social norms did you identify in your contexts?

How do we use Social Norms in Behaviour Change Interventions?

Learning through examples

Which message is more effective?

CHORIZO confirms: The positive message is more effective!

- **Positive** messages **reduced food waste by 11%**.
- **Waste increased by 24%** for **provocative** messages.

It is proven also by other studies that positive framing is more effective, than a provocative one.

Setting:

- Test in Norwegian 8 Strawberry Hotels
- The influence of various messages relating to social norms at the breakfast buffet was tested.

Consider the Framing of Social Norms

Consider the Framing of Social Norms

Which framing works best, depends on many factors, such as

- the norm itself
- the target group
- the environment of the behaviour
- competing social norms

Consider the Framing of Social Norms

Rules of thumb:

- **Dynamic framing** is more **suitable for new norms** in competition with prevalent norms.
- **Paring the statements with visual cues** can increase effectiveness.
- **Negative framing should focus on undesirable behaviours**, and not convey negative pictures to promote a desired behaviour.
- **Different target groups will respond differently** to the same intervention.

There is always the need to test your interventions!

Reflection Time

**Take a minute to reflect
on what you just learned**

What was new?

What moved you?

What will you remember
and take home so far?

Wrap up from the theory

Social norms are unwritten rules which influence people's everyday behaviour.

Know your target: Social norms work by copying others (**descriptive**) or by adapting to an expected rule (**injunctive**)

It's the how that counts! Framing social norms makes a difference (**positive** or **negative**, **static** or **dynamic**). Always test and then evaluate.

BREAK

Reducing food waste with social norms

Plan an intervention with our 8 step approach

8 steps for interventions

8 steps for interventions

1. Define your objective

Images © Canva

8 steps for interventions

Images © Canva

8 steps for interventions

injunctive: we care together (values)

Social norm: Saving food is cool

8 steps for interventions

Miro & Breakout Rooms

Over to you! Time to practice designing a social norm informed intervention

2 Developing an 8-step intervention plan

Instructions:

In your group:

- Read "Description", "Step 1" and "Step 2".
- Then focus on Step 3 and 4 and fill out the fields with your group

Setting:

- It's again a self-organized group work
- Please assign one person to give a 1-minute pitch of your intervention in the plenary

Miro & Breakout Rooms

Dive deeper into one of three scenarios

Scenario 1: Good Provider Identity (Food service)

Group 1, 4

Scenario 2: Good Provider Identity (cities)

Group 2, 5

Scenario 3: Good Provider Identity (schools)

Group 3, 6

How to get there:

1. click on the miro [link](#) in the chat
2. click "join break out room" in zoom
3. on miro: go to board 2 and click the arrow next to your group number

Miro & Breakout Rooms

Welcome back!

1 minute pitch & time to discuss

Scenario 1: Good Provider
Identity (**Food service**)

Group 1, 4

Scenario 2: Good Provider
Identity (**cities**)

Group 2, 5

Scenario 3: Good Provider
Identity (**schools**)

Group 3, 6

Chorizo Tools

Board Game/Datahub/Helpdesk ...

Board Game & Hack your School Lunch

Board Game – Food Waste An educational board game

Hack Your School Lunch - Education material for teachers

Matematik, Madkundskab & Madspild
En samling af læringsforløb for Folkeskolen

2

Mathematics, food literacy & Food Waste
A collection of teaching materials for primary school

Hack Your School-Lunch

Subjects / Themes included: Home economics, SDGs focused activities, and STEM subjects such as Science, Math, or Design. Grades: 6, 7 and 8
Language: English
Can be used in project-based learning (out of subject teaching): Yes
Hours required (total): 4 hours – 3 lessons. If you want to include “Design a school meal” for food donations, please add 2 hours
Materials and facilities needed: Room, paper & writing materials, kitchen scales, kitchen for the design part

Background & Introduction - why is this topic important?

AIM OF SCIENCE EDUCATIONAL PACKAGE

To deliver more engaging & effective social-norms-focused communication and school science education, to prevent/reduce FLW

To create learning and engagement among kids at school around the SDG12.3 Food Waste using the preferred school language and the digital EdTech language

Datahub

EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS / Food waste by Young people...

Food waste by Young people (School Food Waste) data from Workshop with pupils

Followers

0

Data layer

EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Dataset

Groups

PRIVATE

Contact

Food waste by Young people (School Food Waste) data from Workshop with pupils

Results were obtained from the student workshop focused on the "Future of School Food" during the Danish people meeting.

Data and Resources

Wkshop01-PUPILS-WORKSHOP.CS4-DK.pdf

Results were obtained from the student workshop focused on the "Future of...

Contact

Wkshop02-PUPILS-NEWS.CS4-DK.docx

Results were obtained from the Danish news which was based on the school food...

Contact

Future School Food

School Food Lunch Pack

School Food Policy

School Food Waste

Young People Food Waste

How can you use it?

Visualizer

- 1 Select the **eating environment** you want to explore

- 2 Explore the **functionalities**

Guidance Documents & Newsletters

[Link to guidance documents](#)

[Link to newsletter](#)

Helpdesk

Welcome to the CHORIZO Helpdesk

Here, you can find all the relevant information about how CHORIZO can support you in implementing actions to reduce food waste in the context of social norms.

You need help?

We can help you to plan and implement your social-norm and food-waste related interventions. Get in contact with helpdesk.chorizo@cscp.org to receive direct support.

What do we offer?

As a HORIZON EU-funded project, we provide you with free, on-demand and bilateral support in implementing food-waste related interventions.

Questions?

Next steps and check-out

Capacity Building

Next Steps

Fill out our [Feedback Survey](#) to receive a **certificate**

CHORIZO Capacity Building Program Session - Feedback Survey

Access the [Miro board](#) and explore Chorizo free resources

Join our **DeepAction Capacity Building session online in July 2**, Details will be shared soon. You can register [here](#)

Join the **LinkedIn group** [here](#)

Need help? Have questions?
Email us: helpdesk.chorizo@cscp.org

Check out

One sentence in the chat:

What do you take home?

Thank you!

CHORIZO PROJECT

